

Dynamic PFO Shunting In Cryptogenic Stroke: ICE Resolves TEE Diagnostic Discrepancy

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Description

The above images were obtained during the work-up of recurrent cryptogenic ischemic stroke in an elderly patient. The electrocardiogram (EKG, Figure A) revealed sinus rhythm, right axis deviation, low voltage throughout and nonspecific T wave abnormalities.

Transthoracic echocardiography image (TTE, Figure B) with bubble study in the apical 4-chamber view revealed right-to-left shunting suggestive of a patent foramen ovale (PFO). Transesophageal echocardiography (TEE, Figure C) however showed no shunting, likely due to pressure gradient dynamics favoring left atrial dominance during the procedure with inadequate Valsalva maneuver due to sedation.

Intracardiac echocardiography (ICE, Figure D) during PFO closure preparation confirmed an intermittently shunting PFO tunnel, opening only when right atrial pressure exceeded left atrial pressure. The PFO was successfully closed percutaneously with a 30-mm Cardioform PFO occlude device, with no residual shunt by ICE.

Discussion

Cryptogenic stroke accounts for 25-40% of ischemic strokes and remains a diagnostic challenge, particularly when associated with a PFO [1]. PFO is a remnant of fetal circulation which allows right-to-left shunting, potentially enabling paradoxical emboli to cause stroke in patients without conventional risk factors [2]. Shunting is often pressure-dependent, occurring when right atrial pressure exceeds left atrial pressure, such as during Valsalva or transient hemodynamic shifts [3]. TTE with bubble study is commonly used to detect shunts, but TEE may fail to identify them if pressure gradients are unfavorable during testing [4]. ICE provides real-time visualization, offering a solution to resolve diagnostic discrepancies [5].

This case illustrates the diagnostic challenge of pressure-dependent PFO in the setting of cryptogenic stroke. PFO allows paradoxical emboli when right-to-left shunting occurs due to transient increase in right atrial pressure, traditionally provoked by Valsalva or cough maneuvers during echocardiography [1]. While

TTE with bubble study detected a shunt, TEE failed to confirm it likely due to elevated left atrial pressure during TEE exceeding right atrial pressure, with insufficient provocative maneuvers to overcome the pressure difference. This discrepancy highlights TEE's limitations in detecting dynamic PFOs, as its sensitivity depends on the adequacy of provocative maneuvers and hemodynamic conditions [6]. Valsalva and cough maneuvers may not be forceful enough in a sedated patient during TEE, and are often replaced with an abdominal thrust maneuver, factors which may decrease the likelihood of an effective provocative maneuver to cause shunting. Future studies could explore standardized provocative protocols during TEE to improve detection rates.

ICE played a pivotal role, confirming a PFO with intermittent shunting during the closure procedure. ICE's superior real-time visualization in interventional settings allows precise assessment of septal anatomy and shunt dynamics [5]. The intermittent shunting observed in this case aligns with reports describing PFOs with long-tunnel morphology or variable flow, which may evade detection by standard imaging [7]. Successful PFO closure, guided by ICE, obliterated the shunt without complications. PFO closure efficacy in cryptogenic stroke with high-risk PFO features is supported by clinical trials such as the REDUCE trial [8].

Conclusion

There are diagnostic and therapeutic challenges of pressure-dependent PFO in cryptogenic stroke. Discrepancy between a positive TTE and a negative TEE bubble study, likely due to transient atrial pressure gradients, underscores the potential limitations of standard echocardiographic imaging. ICE can be critical in confirming an intermittently shunting PFO and guiding successful percutaneous closure to eliminate the shunt. This approach is an effective strategy for select patients with cryptogenic stroke and high-risk PFO features to reduce the risk of recurrent stroke. Clinicians should remain vigilant of dynamic shunting as a cause of conflicting echocardiographic findings,

and the role of advanced imaging like ICE in resolving such conflict, to ensure accurate diagnosis and optimal management.

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